

Decolonization of Arctic Library and Archives Metadata (DALAM) Thematic Network Update: October 2023 - April 2024

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DALAM Organization and Administration

Meetings

DALAM held two educational sessions (November 2023 and April 2024) and two business meetings (January and February 2024), having taken a break over the winter solstice.

Membership Update

Since our last report, DALAM has welcomed four new members: Merideth Fletcher (Library and Archives Canada), replacing Annie Wolfe, who has moved on to another position; Rebekah Ingram (Carleton University, Canada); Rachael Lorna Johnstone (University of Akureyri); and Sarah Papple (Memorial University of Newfoundland, Labrador Campus)

As of January 1, 2024, DALAM had 31 members from 10 countries: Canada, Denmark, Finland, Germany, Greenland, Iceland, Norway, Sweden, United Kingdom, and United States.

Communications, Outreach, Education/Training

Since our last update, there have been two publications and two presentations related to DALAM.

Publications

Campbell, SM. "Decolonization of Arctic Library and Archives Metadata (DALAM) Thematic Network Update: September 2023", Polar Libraries Bulletin, Fall 2023, p. 7, 8.

Parikka, S. "DALAM at the 2023 IFLA WLIC", Polar Libraries Bulletin, Fall 2023, Issue 88, p. 11.

Presentations

Brillant, S. [Vocabulaire décrivant les Peuples autochtones \(RVM\) : une méthodologie sur-mesure, un projet hors du commun / Subject-headings describing Indigenous Peoples in the RVM : a tailor-made methodology, an extraordinary project](#) Ontario Library Association (OLA) Superconference 2024, Toronto, ON. January 25th, 2024 (in person, 7 participants).

Christoffersen, S. DALAM: Thematic Network on Decolonization of Arctic Library and Archives Metadata. Poster presentation. Arctic Observation Summit, Edinburgh, March 27 - 29, 2024.

Educational Activities

At the November meeting, members from Alaska, Rebecca Moorman, David Cox II, Lisa Digou, and special guest Community Liaison Hope Roberts, presented the work of the Alaska Native Subject Headings Grant Project. This project, which has received two rounds of funding, was designed to work towards identifying and replacing inappropriate subject headings. The project is working towards an Alaska Native Subject Headings website, which would make their work public.

At the April 10 meeting, Sharon Rankin (McGill University) presented the Omeka website (pilot

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About My Library: Arctic Centre Library *continued*

The most challenging clientele are the international and Finnish researchers at the AC who are used to excellent, personal, and quick service. The research combines approaches from the human, social, legal, and natural sciences. It is organized into four research programmes: **Arctic Politics and Development; Arctic Societies: Past, Present, Future; Global Change;** and **Just Green Transition.** Afternoon Coffee Chats are organized weekly to keep the AC staff up to date about ongoing research and other common issues.

The Staff

The only person working in the library is Mr. Arto Kiurujoki, Information Service Secretary. He works closely together with the LUC University Library staff in matters like interlibrary lending or deep diving into information retrieval.

Arto Kiurujoki says about his work: "The library is quiet at the moment; the tourists have disappeared for a while. Researchers and students are busy—summer and holidays are already in mind. But the books don't disappear—a customer just returned six bags of books!

The snow melts, plants grow in the heat of the sun, and the birds sing. What could be nicer than searching for information about all these subjects that belong to the Arctic ecosystems, e.g., Lapin tiira (Lapland's tern), tunturiunikko (Arctic Poppy), sinirikko (Purple Saxifrage), vaivaiskoivu (Draw Birch), lumihyppiäinen (Entomobrya nivalis) or about great explorers: Nordenskiöld, Nansen, Castrén...? These remain in your memory for a few weeks; then the details are forgotten. In the Arctic Centre Library you can find things, that—following the words of the Finnish song—never cease to amaze and puzzle a small wanderer."

Arctic Centre Library. Photo by Marko Junttila.

DALAM Thematic Network Update *continued*

phase) that she and Robin Desmeules have created for DALAM. The site includes three collections: Research resources, Thesauri, and Education resources. The group had much discussion about various attributes of the site. There is still much to be decided, so the discussion will continue in May. In the long term the goal is to have an open site which will be available to anyone looking for Arctic-related decolonization resources.

Looking Forward

The first day of the Polar Libraries Colloquy 2024, in Tromsø, Norway June 10, 2024, will be focused on Sami People and Northern Indigenous People. The DALAM biennial in-person Thematic Network meeting will take place in the afternoon. There is an open [Discussion Topic Poll](#) available in which DALAM members can identify questions or issues that they would like to have discussed at the DALAM in-person meeting. (The workshop is open to all Colloquy participants.)